

COVID-19, STATE GUIDANCE DOCUMENTS ON RELIGIOUS SERVICES, AND THE POTENTIAL OF PRE-INFRINGEMENT ENGAGEMENT WITH RELIGIOUS COMMUNITIES

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Does the coronavirus pandemic justify the government telling churches how to run their worship services? That's a question I asked during the North American reopening phase of summer 2020, on which I found some very concerning aspects to the policy precedents being implemented. I reframe that in some different ways today, thinking of some of the subsequent shutdowns and re-openings and also, more generally, of the possible import into religious freedom contexts of norms from some other areas of law.

Notably, I want to discuss ideas related to consultation with affected communities in advance of the implementation of policies that harm those communities. There is significant legal doctrine on this norm in the context of Indigenous communities.² While I do not necessarily argue for making that norm justiciable in the context of religious communities, I nonetheless suggest that it is a norm that should provide guidance to state actors in the church/state interface in situations like those that arose with COVID-19.

Obviously, as fall and winter of 2020–21 came on, questions of emergency shutdowns became relevant once again, and the various waves and phases of COVID-19 generated distinctive issues. Important religious freedom law bears on various matters that arose, with one very constructive decision relatively earlier in the process being the late November 2020 United States Supreme Court decision in *Roman Catholic Diocese of Brooklyn. v. Cuomo* identifying constitutional problems with New York State's restrictions on attendance at worship service.³ Good decisions have been ready to apply core principles of religious freedom sensibly even amid a pandemic. But the issues raised by COVID-19 have also highlighted issues giving rise to needs for recognition of additional principles and norms.

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2. See some of my past work, cited at note 14, below.

3. *Roman Catholic Diocese of Brooklyn v. Cuomo*, 592 U.S. (2020) was released November 25, 2020.

While the analysis in this paper mainly discusses examples from the summer 2020 reopening phase, it may also bear on subsequent measures. What was different about the summer 2020 reopening, the fall 2020 second wave, and subsequent developments compared to the first wave in March 2020, though, is that there has been time to plan and potentially to dialogue on aspects of the policies adopted. While nobody would deny that COVID-19 presents an ongoing “emergency” in certain senses, different phases of a longer-term emergency can differ in terms of the amount of time available to prepare for them, and that has implications for appropriate state engagement with religious actors.

Some state governments in the United States and provincial and territorial governments in Canada seem to have thought during the summer 2020 reopening phase of the pandemic that they could simply decide how to regulate worship services. In my view, this set a concerning precedent of relatively detailed governmental regulation of religion. Other governments, facing the same coronavirus pandemic, managed to engage with religious institutions more respectfully, furthering health goals during that phase of the emergency without imposing detailed requirements on religious services.

To set the context, I will discuss some striking examples of how coronavirus guidance documents on religious services have differed in ways that show differing levels of respect for principles of state non-interference in religion. While the pandemic situation can obviously justify some steps that would not normally be taken, the different approaches illustrate that governments have had genuine choices about whether to interfere more or to interfere less with religion. The choices they are making have implications in relation to the precedent for future interference.

The documents under discussion, issued by essentially every state government, come under different names that are not applied consistently. Some are “guidelines”, and some are “guidance” documents. But some of the slightly-more gently named “guidance” documents contain significant mandatory restrictions. For example, California’s July 2020 guidance document included this significant restriction with mandatory language: “Places of worship must therefore discontinue indoor singing and chanting activities”.⁴

Slightly different regulations on singing during worship services appeared in two other states. The state of Washington’s phase 1/2/3 guidelines

4. California Department of Public Health, “COVID-19 Industry Guidance: Places of Worship and Providers of Religious Services and Cultural Ceremonies” (July 29, 2020), <<https://files.covid19.ca.gov/pdf/guidance-places-of-worship.pdf>> (copy on file with author).

banned choirs, but specifically permitted masked congregational singing.⁵ The written guidelines of New York State in the initial reopening phase and on through to now required a ban on singing unless a twelve-foot distance could be maintained between individuals.⁶ But most states seemed to suppose that the coronavirus could be controlled during the reopening phase without specific regulation of worship music, which raises some questions about the handful of states that did regulate this aspect of worship.

Some jurisdictions imposed requirements on those offering religious services to record contact information for those attending. For example, the District of Columbia's June 2020 guidance document required that contact details be kept for thirty days and provided a specific mandate that "[f]aith community leadership is responsible for ensuring there is a process in place to account for the names of every person who has been on the premises".⁷ Needless to say, a willingness to register attendance at a place of worship might vary between those more definitively in the flock and those who might have more casually visited without wishing to identify themselves. Some could also worry about the precedent for more concerning governmental uses of religious service registration lists.

A number of states offered guidance on not sharing microphones. Some entered into more concerning regulation of liturgical or sacramental objects, even if naming these objects indirectly. Virginia's Phase One guidance document provided that "[a]ny items used to distribute food or beverages must be disposable and used only once and discarded."⁸ Some Canadian provinces were ready to be more explicit. For example, Alberta's May 2020 document set out a number of rules specifically for food or drink during "a faith-based ritual (e.g. communion)."⁹

5. State of Washington, "Phase 1, Phase 2, and Phase 3 Religious and Faith-Based Organization COVID-19 Requirements" (October 21, 2020 update), <<https://www.governor.wa.gov/sites/default/files/COVID19%20Phase%201%20to%203%20Religious%20and%20Faith%20Based%20OrganizationGuidance.pdf>> (copy on file with author).

6. New York State Department of Health, "Interim Guidance for Religious & Funeral Services During the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency" (April 6, 2021 version), <<https://www.governor.ny.gov/sites/default/files/atoms/files/ReligiousandFuneralServicesMasterGuidance.pdf>> (copy on file with author).

7. Government of the District of Columbia, DC Health, "Phase Two Guidance: Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) Guidance for Places of Worship" (June 16, 2020), <https://www.nationalshrine.org/wp-content/uploads/COVID-19_DC_Health_Guidance_for_Places_of_Worship__2020.06.17_ForPOSTING.pdf> (copy on file with author).

8. Virginia, "Safer at Home: Phase One, Religious Services" (2020), <<https://www.governor.virginia.gov/media/governorvirginiagov/governor-of-virginia/pdf/Virginia-Forward-Phase-One-Religious-Services-Guidelines.pdf>> (copy on file with author).

9. Alberta, "COVID-19 Information: Guidance for Places of Worship" (May 23, 2020), <<https://open.alberta.ca/dataset/2be831dd-d83e-42da-b634-6bc6d5232d1a/resource/dc6e8a2e-978b-4121-acc7-8889fcfc160e/download/covid-19-relaunch-guidance-places-of-worship-2020-05.pdf>> (copy on file with author).

Appropriate guidelines on communion are no doubt entirely sensible from a health standpoint—and are probably so even apart from a pandemic. But it is a highly delicate matter for the state to impose mandatory rules on liturgical and sacramental objects. Again, it puts the state in a position that generates a worrying precedent for how the government can regulate even the most intimate parts of religious services.

Some states, when facing the reopening phase of the coronavirus, engaged very differently with religious entities. Tennessee’s guidance for houses of worship opened with an affirmation of the value of communities of faith and their First Amendment rights, and it went on to explain that the document itself was “an aggregation of suggested protocols from various faith communities across Tennessee” that was offered as a “courtesy for your convenience.”¹⁰ Other documents were clear that they encouraged or recommended practices rather than mandating them—here, one could mention examples like the Wyoming guidelines¹¹ or the Indiana guidelines (which also contained a reminder of the “right of Hoosiers to worship and freely exercise their religion”).¹² Oklahoma’s guidance document for places of worship made specific room for the “discretion” and “best judgment” of religious leaders.¹³

The respect shown in such documents for the freedom of the church—or, more broadly, the sphere of jurisdiction of religious entities separate from the state—is in stark contrast to the regulation of specifically scorned acts (like “singing and chanting activities”), the imposition of state-mandated registries of attendees at worship sites, and mandatory regulations imposed on liturgical and sacramental objects. Federalism thus seemingly revealed some sharply differing governmental attitudes toward religion and toward the church-state interaction.

Differences in attitude were apparent from the outset of the pandemic, as some governments treated religion as offering an “essential service” and others were ready to shut it down. Approaches in that time period present some different issues in so far as they concerned an urgent response in the context of a great deal of uncertainty in March 2020. But differenc-

10. Tennessee, Governor’s Office of Faith-Based and Community Initiatives, “Guidance for Gathering Together in Houses of Worship” (October 2020), <<https://www.tn.gov/content/dam/tn/governorsoffice-documents/House%20of%20Worship%20Guidance%20FBCI.pdf>> (copy on file with author).

11. Wyoming, “COVID-19: Guidance for Faith Organizations and Funeral Homes from the Wyoming Department of Health” (August 1, 2020), <<https://health.wyo.gov/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/WDH-COVID-19-Guidance-for-Faith-Organizations-and-Funeral-Homes-8.1.2020.pdf>> (copy on file with author).

12. Indiana, “Revised Guidance for Places of Worship” (2020), https://www.backontrack.in.gov/files/BackOnTrack-IN_PlacesOfWorship.pdf (copy on file with author).

13. Oklahoma, “Guidance for Oklahoma’s Open Up and Recover Safely Plan: Places of Worship” (May 1, 2020).

es in attitude that persisted during the fall 2020 reopening phase, second wave, and subsequent phases, when there was more clarity and more time for dialogue, raise some major questions. Some governments sought to minimize their impacts on religion and others either did not worry about their impact or even maximized it.

In another human rights context, that concerning Indigenous rights, there has been the development of significant bodies of norms and laws on the concept of pre-infringement consultation with Indigenous communities. Canada, especially, has seen the development of a very substantial body of case law on what is called the duty to consult doctrine.¹⁴ The idea of this doctrine is to minimize negative effects on Indigenous communities' rights by requiring governments to proactively consult with them when contemplating government decisions that carry the possibility of an adverse impact on Indigenous rights.

Just what is required in terms of consultation is calibrated under the Canadian law on this doctrine in respect of factors allowing an analysis of the potential degree of adverse impact on rights, although the application of this analysis has not always been straightforward or free of controversy.¹⁵ But what is always sought is what is called “meaningful consultation”, which involves the government genuinely providing information on what is being contemplated, listening to responses concerning potential impacts of the potential government decision, and then showing evidence of having considered what it has heard in its decision-making process about the government decision and potential variants of it.¹⁶

A key aim underlying this doctrine, as I suggested, is to minimize negative impacts on rights—and it could thus be considered aligned with legal doctrines that call for minimal impairment of rights as part of the test for justified infringements on rights. But it also serves purposes of trying to further reconciliation between Indigenous and non-Indigenous communities in the context of a complex colonial history.

The Canadian body of law I have referenced on the duty to consult has become complex and technical, and I do not in any way suggest

14. I have written extensively on this doctrine in works that have been regularly cited by Canadian courts. See generally Dwight G. Newman, *The Duty to Consult: New Relationships with Aboriginal Peoples* (Saskatoon: Purich, 2009); Dwight G. Newman, *Revisiting the Duty to Consult Aboriginal Peoples* (Vancouver: UBC Press, 2014); Dwight Newman, “The Section 35 Duty to Consult,” in Peter Oliver, Patrick Macklem, and Nathalie des Rosiers, eds., *The Oxford Handbook of the Canadian Constitution* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017).

15. For the original statement of the key tests, see *Haida Nation v. British Columbia* (Minister of Forests), 2004 SCC 73, [2004] 3 SCR 511.

16. See e.g. *Adam v. Canada*, 2014 FC 1185 at para. 70, adopting definition of meaningful consultation from Newman, *Revisiting the Duty to Consult*, p. 103.

importing it directly. It is also important to acknowledge that the issues between the state and religious communities are obviously very different than issues as between the state and Indigenous communities.¹⁷ That said, various misunderstandings between the church and state are increasingly probable as the world shifts not just to a post-Constantinian order or to the separation of church and state, but to a reality with significant secularization, especially pronounced amongst certain layers of governmental bureaucracy. An idea like pre-infringement consultation has the potential to help lessen unnecessary negative impacts on religious liberty and to promote better relationships overall. Adapted away from a justiciable doctrine for present purposes into a norm of governmental practice, pre-infringement engagement with religious communities would seem highly appropriate.

What some states did in their policies during the summer 2020 reopening phase showed this sort of respectful engagement. There are arguments grounded in larger bodies of norms that lend support to what they did. Their approach avoided unnecessary infringements of religious liberty and unnecessary interference with religious communities in so far as they engaged with religious communities on what would work well for all and be respectful of religious freedom. Such an approach also fosters good relationships overall.

This latter point is important in respect of a key objection that could be levelled at parts of my argument. Namely, some would object that states needed to take the steps that they did because some religious congregations did unreasonable things and ended up generating super spreader events. I cannot deny some aspects of this point with respect to some very specific incidents. But the fact that some super spreader events occurred in the context of some risky decisions made at some churches should not be license to prohibit all religious worship for other churches. In some contexts, governmental authorities saw super spreader events at worship services held in basements and then prohibited even drive-in worship services where everyone would remain in closed vehicles. There is room for more expectation of rationality, not to mention even-handedness relative to other sectors, in government decision-making.

Beyond this response, though, I want to suggest that an approach drawing on norms of pre-infringement engagement can actually assist in

17. For some analogies between the distance of both Indigenous and religious worldviews from liberal secular norms, though, see generally R.E. Lowe-Walker, *Intercultural Deliberation and the Politics of Minority Rights* (Vancouver: UBC Press, 2018).

minimizing problems. First of all, religious leaders drawn into dialogue and receiving fair information about health matters in an environment of respect for religious freedom are more likely to cooperate in developing approaches and making decisions that are responsive to this information than those simply subject to state orders that appear to show disrespect for religion.

Second, in so far as the Canadian jurisprudence on the duty to consult doctrine can inform a concept of pre-infringement engagement, it may also have pertinent norms for this point. One of the expectations within the duty to consult doctrine is that there is to be good faith engagement from both sides, and if an Indigenous community does not engage in good faith, it may lose the opportunity to be consulted and the state may no longer face a duty in that context.¹⁸

A norm of pre-infringement engagement could legitimately come with expectations of good faith involvement in the engagement by religious communities. If some chose not to engage in good faith, they might be then subject to legal restrictions without the same respect for their perspectives. But simply restricting religious entities without beginning with respect for them is not an appropriate starting point. A broader body of jurisprudence can be informative to approaches that can achieve greater respect for religious freedom and religious communities while also achieving greater societal cohesion.

It is too easy to say that the pandemic justifies every government act taken in response to it. The very fact that there are varying governmental approaches in the context of religious organizations and religious services shows that this is an arena in which choices are possible. Governments that interfered more in religious services chose to interfere more in religion. That is a concerning development. Even while guidance documents from the reopening phase had sensible ideas that could protect health, the readiness of some governments to make more of those mandatory without engaging with religious communities—even while striking at particular liturgical and sacramental acts or core elements of religious liberty—raises serious questions.

The appropriate response of religious entities is challenging. In some ways, it would not be good for these entities, or for religion generally, to be perceived as fighting against sound health guidance. At the same time,

18. See e.g. *Xats'ull First Nation and Director (Environmental Management Act) and Gibraltar Mines Ltd.*, Decision No. 200-EMA-006(a) (British Columbia Environmental Management Agency) at paras. 343, 358-60.

it is not good for these entities, or for religion generally, to permit without objection the accumulation of precedents for governmental intrusion into core elements of worship services.

My contribution may not reveal easy answers on the path forward, but I hope that it exposes some details of some further dilemmas arising in the context of law, religion, and coronavirus and presents a perspective on a norm that could be advocated and developed by various actors. Churches—and other religious entities—do not and should not want the state regulating aspects of their religious services. But the coronavirus pandemic has provided an opportunity for a development of precedents for such interference that is arguably all the more dangerous for its very subtlety, even while alternative approaches would exist that could lessen the harms.

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